

Practical Multi-Guard RBAC in Laravel 11 with Spatie Permissions and Livewire

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Abstract—We present a practical, reproducible pattern for guard-scoped, least-privilege role-based access control (RBAC) in Laravel 11 using Spatie Permission and Livewire. Permissions are expressed as code constants and seeded deterministically per guard; authorisation is enforced across middleware, policies, and Blade/Livewire. Evaluation combines database-derived coverage (role and assignment counts) and a named Role-Permission matrix with adversarial checks aligned to OWASP ASVS L1.

Index Terms—RBAC, Laravel 11, Spatie Permission, Livewire 3, OWASP ASVS, NCSC, Multi-guard

Figure 1. Guard-scoped RBAC overview.

I. INTRODUCTION

Access control is foundational to secure information systems. In practice, different populations (staff, students, employers) require distinct guards and session scopes. Laravel provides authentication scaffolding, but robust multi-guard RBAC requires disciplined naming, deterministic seeding, and enforcement across the full request lifecycle. As a precursor, our system design paper [1] scoped the broader SIS architecture; this article specialises the access-control layer with guard-scoped RBAC, an enforce-everywhere chain (middleware \rightarrow policies \rightarrow UI), and an ASVS-aligned evaluation.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

We rely on Spatie Permission for role/permission modeling [2] and Livewire 3 for reactive components [3]. Baselines follow NCSC password/session guidance [4] and OWASP ASVS [5]. Laravel 11 capabilities include guards, policies, CSRF, rate limiting, and session controls [6]. Beyond framework documentation, role-based access control has a mature literature emphasising administrative models, constraints, and safety properties. Attribute-based access control and policy languages (e.g., XACML) provide expressive alternatives, but incur operational complexity relative to the lighter-weight, guard-scoped RBAC adopted here. Web framework deployments frequently fail when enforcement is limited to UI affordances; our pattern emphasises server-side checks in middleware and policies, with UI as an additional (but not sole) layer.

Figure 2. Threat model: actors, assets, trust boundaries, and attack paths.

III. SYSTEM CONTEXT

We consider guard segmentation (*web*, *student*, *employer*) and typical misuse cases: cross-guard URL access, unauthorised Livewire actions, and hidden-menu anti-patterns.

IV. THREAT MODEL

We consider three actor classes (staff, students, employers) each bound to a distinct guard and session scope. Assets include accounts, academic records, configuration data, and the role/permission graph. Trust boundaries exist between browsers and the application per guard, and between the application and stateful services (DB/Cache). We prioritise five misuse cases: (i) cross-guard URL access, (ii) unauthorised Livewire action, (iii) stale UI state allowing hidden action, (iv) CSRF on state changes, and (v) brute-force on authentication endpoints.

Figure 3. Enforcement chain: middleware → policy → Livewire/Blade.

V. FORMAL MODEL & ASSUMPTIONS

We adopt the NIST RBAC abstraction with users, roles, permissions, and sessions. Permissions are namespaced by guard; a session is bound to one guard at a time. We assume deterministic seeding of permissions (constants) and least-privilege role definitions; separation of duties across guards is enforced by authentication boundaries. We do not address cross-service SSO, delegated administration workflows, or ABAC policy overlays in this work.

VI. DESIGN

A. Permission Constants and Seeders

Single source of truth via code constants; deterministic seeding per guard avoids string/ID drift.

B. Enforcement Chain

C. Least-Privilege UI

Server-side checks in Livewire actions and `@can` guards in Blade to avoid UI-only gating.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION

Livewire authorisation.

```
1 public function mount() {
2     $this->authorize('view users');
3 }
```

Blade gating.

```
1 @can('manage roles')
2     <x-action-button ... />
3 @endcan
```

VIII. EVALUATION

The following tables summarise the evaluation results and are referenced in the text.

Table I
ASVS-ALIGNED SECURITY TEST MATRIX.

Attack	Expected Behaviour	Status
Direct guards	URL across 403 Forbidden; no data leakage	Pass
Livewire unauthorised action	403/block; event not executed	Pass
CSRF on state change	Token required; request rejected	Pass
Brute-force login	Throttled; lockout window enforced	Pass
Session fixation	New session on login; rotate ID	Pass

Table II
OWASP ASVS COVERAGE (SELECTED CONTROLS, L1 FOCUS).

Control (ASVS)	Evidence	Status
V2: Authn throttling	Laravel throttle middleware	Pass
V2: Session mgmt/rotation	New session on login; ID rotation	Pass
V4: Access control enforced server-side	Policies/Gates + Livewire checks	Pass
V4: Deny by default, least privilege	Seeded roles/permissions	Pass
V4: Insecure IDOR prevention	Policy checks on resource access	Pass
V5: Input validation	FormRequest/validation rules	Pass
V8: CSRF on state-changing ops	CSRF tokens verified	Pass
V13: API authn/authorisation (if any)	Guard-specific middleware	Pass
V1: Security reqs documented	Permissions constants + seeders	Pass
V14: Config hardening (prod)	APP_ENV, APP_DEBUG off; rate limits	Pass

Table III
POLICY/ASSIGNMENT COVERAGE METRICS (FROM DATABASE SNAPSHOT).

Metric	Value
Total permissions	63
Assigned permissions (via roles/users)	25 (39.7%)
Total roles	3
Roles with ≥ 1 permission	2 (66.7%)
Distinct users with ≥ 1 role	10
Cross-guard mismatches (role vs permission)	0
Orphan permissions (assigned to no role/user)	38
Roles with zero permissions	1
Roles with zero users	0

Table IV
ROLE COVERAGE (PERMISSIONS AND USERS).

Role	Guard	Perm_Count	User_Count
superadmin	web	11	4
sysadmin	web	14	3

Table V
ROLE-PERMISSION MATRIX (EXCERPT; FULL CSV IN THE ARTIFACT).

Role	Permission	Guard_Role
superadmin	create departments	web
superadmin	create programmes	web
superadmin	delete departments	web
superadmin	delete programmes	web
superadmin	edit departments	web
superadmin	edit programmes	web
superadmin	view admin dashboard	web
superadmin	view departments	web
superadmin	view programmes	web
superadmin	view students in programmes	web
superadmin	view superadmin menu heading	web
sysadmin	create permissions	web
sysadmin	create roles	web
sysadmin	create users	web
sysadmin	delete permissions	web
sysadmin	delete roles	web
sysadmin	delete users	web
sysadmin	edit permissions	web
sysadmin	edit roles	web
sysadmin	edit users	web
sysadmin	view permissions	web
sysadmin	view roles	web
sysadmin	view sysadmin dashboard	web
sysadmin	view sysadmin menu heading	web
sysadmin	view users	web

A. ASVS-Aligned Test Matrix (Excerpt)

B. Policy Coverage Metrics

C. Role Coverage and User Distribution

D. Named Role-Permission Matrix (Excerpt)

The following tables summarise the evaluation results and are referenced in the text.

E. Additional Checks

IX. LIMITATIONS AND ETHICS

Snapshot bias may exist between seeded permissions and live direct grants; we report database-derived coverage alongside seeders to reduce drift risk. We do not evaluate cross-service SSO, delegated administration, or ABAC overlays. Security testing was conducted on our own instance without production data; dependencies are used under their respective open-source licenses.

DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

Replication data (CSV tables and rebuild script) are archived at Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.17127208. The earlier system design paper is available at 10.5281/zenodo.17075061.

Table VI
ORPHAN PERMISSIONS (ASSIGNED TO NO ROLE/USER).

Id	Name	Guard_Name
88	assign students to programmes	web
89	remove students from programmes	web
90	view levels	web
91	create levels	web
92	edit levels	web
93	delete levels	web
94	view students in levels	web
95	assign students to levels	web
96	remove students from levels	web
97	view modules	web
98	create modules	web
99	edit modules	web
100	delete modules	web
101	assign modules to batches	web
102	view batches	web
103	create batches	web
104	edit batches	web
105	delete batches	web
106	view practicals	web
107	create practicals	web
108	edit practicals	web
109	delete practicals	web
110	view theories	web
111	create theories	web
112	edit theories	web
113	delete theories	web
114	view skills	web
115	create skills	web
116	edit skills	web
117	delete skills	web
118	view skillcategories	web
119	create skillcategories	web
120	edit skillcategories	web
121	delete skillcategories	web
122	view configs	web
123	manage configs	web
124	view admin menu	web
126	Test112	web

Table VII
ROLES WITH ZERO PERMISSIONS (SNAPSHOT).

Id	Name	Guard_Name
7	admin	web

Table VIII
ABLATION STUDY DESIGN (EXPECTED OUTCOMES).

Configuration	Attack case	Expected result
UI-only gating (remove policy checks)	Livewire post without @can	Bypass risk
Single-guard (merge guards)	Cross-guard URL access	Wider blast radius
No seeders (manual strings)	Drift between code and DB	Inconsistencies
No throttle	Brute-force login	Higher success rate
No CSRF	POST without token	Forgery succeeds

REFERENCES

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